

Fries Rearrangement of *o*-Carboxy- β -substituted Phenolic Esters

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Fries rearrangements of 5-methyl-, 5-bromo-, and 5-chloro-2-acetoxybenzoic acids have been effected, affording the corresponding 5-substituted-2-hydroxyacetophenone-3-carboxylic acids. Fries rearrangement of the corresponding 2-propionyloxy analogues have also been studied, the reaction being successful only with 5-methyl-2-propionyloxybenzoic acid. The hydroxyketones thus formed have also been synthesised by the Friedel-Crafts acylation of the appropriate 5-substituted-2-hydroxybenzoic acids.

Fries rearrangement of phenolic esters carrying electro-negative groups fails or proceeds with difficulty¹⁻³. Shah and Shah⁴ investigated the Fries rearrangement of phenolic esters, derived from the three isomeric hydroxybenzoic acids, and reported failure in the case of *m*-acetoxybenzoic acid and success with *o*-acetoxybenzoic acid (aspirin) and *p*-acetoxybenzoic acid. These workers have further reported that the Fries rearrangement of aspirin furnishes only one product, viz., 4-hydroxyacetophenone-3-carboxylic acid. Usually a Fries rearrangement of an *ortho*-substituted phenolic ester with its *para* and second *ortho* positions free affords both the *ortho*- and the *para*-hydroxyketones. The fact that the Fries rearrangement of aspirin does not furnish the *ortho*-migration product suggests that there is probably some effect, which may be steric or polar or both, that inhibits *ortho*-migration totally. To establish this point, a study of the Fries rearrangement of *o*-acetoxybenzoic acid, having the position *para* with respect to the acetoxy group blocked, has been thought necessary and with this aim in view the study of the Fries rearrangement of 5-substituted-2-acetoxy- and -2-propionyloxy-benzoic acids has been undertaken.

The Fries rearrangement of 5-methyl-(I), 5-bromo-(II), and 5-chloro (III)-2-acetoxybenzoic acids has been studied systematically at different temperatures in absence or presence of a solvent like nitrobenzene, using different proportions of anhydrous aluminium chloride. When the reaction was carried out near about 100° and using aluminium chloride and phenolic ester in 1:1 molar ratio, and particularly when the solvent was used, the yields were found very poor. When the conditions of the reaction were made more vigorous by increasing the reaction temperature and the relative proportion of aluminium chloride, the yields of the ketonic products increased. As a result of this study, it has been established that the condition for obtaining optimum yields consists in heating an intimate mixture of the phenolic ester and anhydrous aluminium chloride in 1:3.3 molar

1. Rosenmund and Schnurr, *Annalen*, 1928, 56, 460.
2. Brown, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 872.
3. Amin and Choughulay, *Science & Culture*, 1964, 19, 614.
4. *This Journal*, 1949, 26, 235.

ratio at 165-70° in absence of any solvent. Under these conditions, the Fries rearrangement of (I), (II), and (III) afforded 5-methyl-(IV), 5-bromo-(V), and 5-chloro-(VI) 2-hydroxyacetophenone-3-carboxylic acids in 66, 26, and 18% yield respectively.

The ketonic products of (IV), (V), and (VI), thus formed, dissolve in bicarbonate solution, develop characteristic ferric reaction, provide characteristic ketonic derivative, and afford the corresponding 2'-hydroxychalcones with benzaldehyde; these 2'-hydroxychalcone derivatives have been converted into the corresponding flavonoid compounds by appropriate chemical reactions*. These properties are in conformity with the structures assigned to (IV), (V), and (VI). These hydroxyketonic products have also been synthesised by the Friedel-Crafts acetylation of 5-methyl-, 5-bromo-, and 5-chloro-2-hydroxybenzoic acids in comparatively poor yields.

The Fries rearrangement of 5-methyl-, 5-bromo-, and 5-chloro-2-propionyloxybenzoic acids have also been studied. The reaction proceeded successfully only in the case of 5-methyl-2-propionyloxybenzoic acid, affording 5-methyl-2-hydroxypropiophenone-3-carboxylic acid (VIII). It failed in the other two cases. The ketone (VII) has also been synthesised on the Friedel-Crafts propionylation of 5-methyl-2-hydroxybenzoic acid. The Friedel-Crafts propionylation of 5-bromo- and 5-chloro-2-hydroxybenzoic acids failed.

The results of this investigation suggest that apparently there is no factor which operates to prevent the *ortho*-migration in the phenolic esters (I), (II), and (III) and that inhibition caused by presence of an electro-negative carboxyl group can be overcome to a certain extent by selecting more vigorous conditions for the reaction³. Failure of the Fries rearrangement of 5-chloro- and 5-bromo-2-propionyloxybenzoic acids can be

attributed to the decreased electrophilicity of the migrating $\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ || \\ -\text{C}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_3 \\ \oplus \end{array}$ group as compared to the $\begin{array}{c} \text{O} \\ || \\ -\text{C}-\text{CH}_3 \\ \oplus \end{array}$ and to the decreased overall electron-availability in the benzene ring in these two cases as compared to that in the case of their 5-methyl analogue. This latter factor would also provide an explanation for the observed order of the decrease in the yields in the Fries rearrangement of compounds (I), (II), and (III).

EXPERIMENTAL

Fries Rearrangement of 2-Acetoxy-5-methylbenzoic Acid: 5-Methyl-2-Hydroxyacetophenone-3-carboxylic Acid (IV). Method (a) (in absence of any solvent).—A mixture of 2-acetoxy-5-methylbenzoic acid (19.5 g., 1 *M*) and finely powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (44.0 g., 3.3 *M*) was heated at 170° for 3 hr., cooled, and decomposed with ice and HCl. The solid separating was filtered, washed, and crystallised from ethanol in white needles, m.p. 134°, yield 12 g. (61%).

*This work constitutes the subject matter of another communication which will be published soon. S. Joshi and Singh, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 4993.

Method (b) (using nitrobenzene as solvent).—A suspension of 2-acetoxy-5-methylbenzoic acid (19.5 g., 1 *M*) and finely powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (22.0 g., 1.5 *M*) in freshly distilled nitrobenzene (50 ml) was heated at 120° for 6 hr., cooled, and decomposed with ice and HCl. The nitrobenzene layer was separated, washed with water, and extracted repeatedly with bicarbonate solution (10%). The white solid mass separating on acidification was collected and crystallised from ethanol in white needles, m.p. 134°, yield 6.0 g. (30%). It dissolved in bicarbonate solution and showed a positive ferric reaction. (Found: C, 61.9; H, 5.2. C₁₀H₁₀O₄ requires C, 61.8; H, 5.1%).

Friedel-Crafts Acetylation of 2-Hydroxy-5-methylbenzoic Acid: Formation of (IV).—To a mixture of 2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzoic acid (7.5 g., 0.5 *M*), anhydrous aluminium chloride (20.0 g., 1.5 *M*), and freshly distilled nitrobenzene (60 ml) acetyl chloride (5 ml) was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was left overnight and then heated on a water bath for 3 hr. It was worked up as under method (b). The white solid, thus obtained, was washed several times with hot water to remove unchanged 2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzoic acid. It was crystallised from ethanol in white needles, m.p. 134°, yield 3.0 g. (31%); mixed m.p. with the same obtained as above remained unchanged. The 2,4-*DNP* of (IV) was crystallised from ethanol in orange-yellow needles, m.p. 157°. (Found: N, 14.8. C₁₆H₁₄O₇N₄ requires N, 14.9%).

Fries Rearrangement of 2-Acetoxy-5-bromobenzoic Acid: 2-Hydroxy-5-bromoacetophenone-3-carboxylic Acid (V).—This reaction was carried out following method (a), described previously. The product obtained was crystallised from ethanol in white needles, m.p. 145-46°, yield 26%. It dissolved with effervescence in bicarbonate solution and developed a deep violet colour with ethanolic ferric chloride.

It was also synthesised in 14% yield by the Friedel-Crafts acetylation of 2-hydroxy-5-bromobenzoic acid by following method (b). (Found: Br, 30.65. C₉H₇O₄Br requires Br, 30.9%). 2,4-*DNP* of (V) was crystallised from acetic acid in yellow granules, m.p. 255°. (Found: N, 12.55. C₁₃H₁₁O₇N₄Br requires N, 12.7%).

Fries Rearrangement of 2-Acetoxy-5-chlorobenzoic Acid: 2-Hydroxy-5-chloroacetophenone-3-carboxylic Acid (VI).—This reaction was effected by following the conditions described under method (a). It was crystallised from ethanol in white needles, m.p. 139-40°, yield 18%. It dissolved with effervescence in bicarbonate solution and developed a deep violet colour with ethanolic ferric chloride solution.

It was also formed in 10% yield by the Friedel-Crafts acetylation of 2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzoic acid, following method (b). (Found: Cl, 16.35. C₉H₇O₄Cl requires Cl, 16.5%). The 2,4-*DNP* of (VI) was crystallised from ethanol in red cubic crystals, m.p. 190°. (Found: Cl, 9.15. C₁₅H₁₁O₇N₄Cl requires Cl, 9.0%).

2-Propionyloxy-5-methylbenzoic acid was obtained on heating 2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzoic acid (5 g.) with propionic anhydride (8 ml) in presence of a drop of pyridine on a steam bath for 2 hr. It was crystallised from ethanol in white needles, m.p. 104°. (Found: C, 63.90; H, 5.90. C₁₁H₁₂O₄ requires C, 63.46, H, 5.76%).

Fries Rearrangement of 2-Propionyloxy-5-methylbenzoic Acid: Formation of 2-Hydroxy-5-methylpropioacetophenone-3-carboxylic Acid (VII).—The reaction was carried out, following

method (a). It was crystallised from ethanol in pinkish white needles, m.p. 110°, yield 30%. It dissolved with effervescence in bicarbonate solution and developed a deep violet colour with ferric chloride solution.

It was also obtained in about 15% yield on the Friedel-Crafts propionylation of 2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzoic acid. (Found: C, 63.90; H, 6.00. $C_{11}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 63.46; H 5.76%). The 2,4-DNP of (VII) was crystallised from ethanol in deep orange-yellow needles, m.p. 230°. (Found: N, 14.25. $C_{17}H_{16}O_7N_4$ requires N, 14.40%).

2-Propionyloxy-5-chlorobenzoic acid, obtained from 2-hydroxy-5-chlorobenzoic acid, as described above, was crystallised from ethanol in white needles, m.p. 149°. (Found: Cl, 15.4. $C_{10}H_9O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 15.5%).

2-Propionyloxy-5-bromobenzoic acid was formed, as described above, from 2-hydroxy-5-bromobenzoic acid. It was crystallised from ethanol in small white needles, m.p. 154°. (Found: Br, 29.1. $C_{10}H_9O_4Br$ requires Br, 29.30%).

The Fries rearrangement of 5-chloro- and 5-bromo-2-propionyloxybenzoic acids failed. The Friedel-Crafts propionylation of 5-chloro- and 5-bromo-2-hydroxybenzoic acids also failed.

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